

Hybridization through ohmic heating of a cascade PCM-TES for a CSP plant

SolarPACES

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1. Introduction

In the current global context, renewable technologies are essential to the future energy mix. For solar based technologies, the actual cost of PV plants makes CSP plants noncompetitive unless energy storage is considered. As a matter of fact, the excess of non-dispatchable renewable energy in the grid is starting to become an issue in countries with high solar radiation, such as Spain. This situation presents an opportunity for CSP with its easy storage integration to be able to provide renewable energy on demand. The ability to store excess electricity from the grid can further increase the value of this technology, granting to CSP the possibility to absorb excess electricity from non-dispatchable sources that otherwise will be lost. This paper presents a storage concept for CSP based in Phase Change Materials (PCM) in cascade configuration and an ohmic heating electrification mechanism for its hybridization.

2. Storage concept

The proposed storage uses both the sensible and latent heat energy of inorganic salts used as PCMs in a cascade configuration to reduce the thermal hysteresis between the charge and discharge phases of the plant (Figure 1, left). To further reduce this thermal hysteresis, a last electrified step can be included which will be charged electrically and discharged thermally (Figure 1, right). The number of steps and the PCM selected for each of them depends on the CSP plant. At least one suitable candidate in the range of 300 °C to 600 °C typically used in CSP plants has been identified.

Figure 1 Distribution of sensible and latent heat in a PCM-sensible heat exchanger in cascade configuration. Left: standard cascade; right: electrified cascade.

One of the well-known challenges of the PCM storage systems is the low thermal conductivity of the inorganic salts used as storage media. To solve this issue without incurring high costs, a composite of PCM and metal wools is proposed. Metal wools can highly increase the global thermal conductivity of the composite [1] and are inexpensive and available.

3. Hybridization: Ohmic heating

The metal wools used as heat enhancers are continuous and have a preferential direction, which allows for establishing a current between its ends and generate heat through the Joule effect (ohmic heating) with an appropriate configuration of the metal wools in the storage, this effect can be used for hybridization. Due to the low electric resistance of the wools, high currents are generated with small voltages, requiring large electric fields for effective ohmic heating. After the first studies have been conducted in collaboration with ExHEAT®, a series of challenges have been detected.

- The fibers of the metal wools are not regular due to the nature of its fabrication, with larger and smaller sections mixed. The different sections imply different currents for a defined voltage, which difficult the control of the system.
- The inorganic salts used as PCM are typically corrosive. Even when a good compatibility pair wool-PCM is selected, some corrosion is expected. This corrosion will further modify the section of the wools with time and not necessarily in a uniform way. These irregularities in the section of each wool imply different electric resistances and pose a challenge to controllability.
- When subjected to a voltage, the PCM material also participates with ions as charge carriers. Since the electrical resistance of the inorganic salts is much higher than for the metal wools, this heating effect is negligible. Nevertheless, the electrical conductivity of the salts in solid state and liquid state is typically different, generating different electric resistances depending on the melting front. This is also a challenge in controllability.
- If the metal wools are not perfectly in contact with the HTF tubes or the container shell, electric arcs can appear, degrading metal elements.
- Electric insulation is also a concern since the storage system is connected to the rest of the plant through metal pipes that can divert electricity. This is particularly challenging when the nature of the HTF used in CSP is corrosive, limiting the available materials for pipe insulation.

4. Conclusions

A PCM storage system in cascade configuration is proposed to hybridize CSP plants increasing its market value. This system uses metal wools to cope in a cheap way with the low thermal conductivity of the PCMs while using these same wools as electric heaters. A study has been conducted and several challenges have been identified to be addressed.

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References

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